

Mechanistic multi-objective optimization of ion-pair reversed-phase liquid chromatography for oligonucleotide purification

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ABSTRACT

Oligonucleotides (ONs) play a vital role in diagnostics and therapeutics, with ion-pair reversed-phase liquid chromatography (IP-RPLC) being a key method for their purification. This study presents a numerical approach to optimize ON purification using both single-objective (productivity) and multi-objective (productivity and yield) optimization. A transport–dispersive column model incorporating a gradient-modified Langmuir kinetic adsorption–desorption isotherm was employed to describe the separation dynamics. The model was validated against experimental elution profiles of a 20-mer ON and its six most abundant shortmer impurities, and then used to optimize injection volume and gradient slope under varying purity constraints. A hybrid optimization strategy combining simulated annealing (stochastic) with the simplex algorithm (deterministic) was applied.

The results showed that productivity was maximized at the highest injection volume, while higher purity constraints required shallower gradient slopes. Multi-objective optimization yielded Pareto fronts with unexpected shapes, including inflection points or local minima. We hypothesize that slow adsorption–desorption kinetics limited the model's ability to accurately describe separations across a broad range of gradient slopes. To test this, two new models were calibrated using only shallow or steep gradient data. The resulting Pareto fronts displayed no inflection points or local minima, supporting our hypothesis.

1. Introduction

Oligonucleotides (ONs) are essential DNA- or RNA-based drugs with increasing therapeutic and diagnostic applications [1–3]. During the synthesis of the full-length product (FLP), numerous impurities are formed. Efficient separation of these impurities on a preparative scale is crucial for achieving high product purity. However, existing methods are often challenging, and balancing both purity and yield remains difficult, if not impossible.

Today's methods for the preparative purification of ONs are ion-exchange chromatography (IEX) and ion-pair reversed-phase liquid chromatography (IP-RPLC) [4]. In this study, the focus will be on IP-RPLC. Regardless of the chromatographic mode, all methods require optimization to achieve high productivity. Method optimization can be performed experimentally, empirically, or through numerical simulations using mechanistic models. In this study, mechanistic models are used for method optimization.

Modeling liquid chromatography is essential for understanding separation mechanisms and optimizing analytical and preparative systems [5]. Preparative chromatography is more complex than analytical chromatography due to the limited column surface capacity, leading to nonlinear conditions and asymmetric elution bands at high solute concentrations [5,6]. Competition for surface area further affects band shape and retention [5]. Simulating nonlinear conditions requires a column model with accurate adsorption/desorption descriptions [7,8]. Compared with analytical chromatography, mathematical modeling of ON separations has been less explored [8–10].

Our recent research focused on developing and evaluating various adsorption isotherm models with which to predict the overloaded concentration profiles of ONs eluted in IP-RPLC [8]. This investigation pursued two distinct approaches: (i) testing a comprehensive model suitable for fundamental research and (ii) using simpler models more suitable for process optimization. The simpler models reduce the effort required for model validation and decrease the computation time during

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optimization. Consequently, the second approach focused on developing and testing modified Langmuir isotherm models adapted for gradient mode and IP-RPLC. Building on this foundation, the current study extends the focus to optimizing ON separations.

Optimizing chromatographic productivity is challenging because it requires many repeated simulations of process dynamics. To complete the optimization in a reasonable timeframe, the method must efficiently identify the global optimum—or at least a near-optimal solution—with as few evaluations as possible. The complexity of the objective function is also a key factor: when the global optimum is hidden among many local optima, the problem becomes more difficult to solve. Deterministic methods (e.g., simplex, Newton-Raphson) are fast due to rapid convergence, but they are prone to getting stuck in local optima. Stochastic methods (e.g., simulated annealing, genetic algorithms) are more suitable for complex search landscapes but typically require more evaluations. For such cases, or in multi-objective optimization, stochastic or hybrid strategies are generally more robust [11].

To combine broad search capability with efficient local refinement, we employed a hybrid optimization approach in this study that integrates simulated annealing and the simplex algorithm. Simulated annealing explores the solution space probabilistically, enabling it to escape local optima. Once a promising region is located, the simplex algorithm efficiently refines the solution using a geometric search strategy.

This hybrid approach leverages the exploratory strength of stochastic methods and the rapid convergence of deterministic ones. Its effectiveness in chromatographic optimization has been previously demonstrated [12], including comparative studies showing faster convergence and improved solution quality over purely stochastic techniques such as random search [13]. It is also worth mentioning that a related hybrid optimization strategy was previously applied by the authors to simpler chromatographic systems, including enantiomeric separations of omeprazole and etiracetam [14]; however, the current study extends its application to the more complex case of multi-component oligonucleotide separations.

Optimization often begins with a single objective – typically finding the best experimental settings for controllable variables to maximize or minimize an objective function, subject to constraints such as purity and yield. In chromatographic applications, productivity is frequently used as the primary objective function [5,6]. However, real-world problems often involve conflicting objectives, motivating the use of more advanced approaches such as multi-objective optimization.

The Pareto-optimal approach addresses these trade-offs by identifying solutions where improvement in one objective necessarily compromises another. The Pareto front represents the set of non-dominated, optimal trade-off solutions—forming a boundary beyond which no objective can be improved without degrading another [15–17]. A Pareto plot visualizes this front, often as a curve or surface, and illustrates the inherent compromises between competing responses. In oligonucleotide (ON) production, where feedstock is costly, maximizing yield is particularly important; otherwise, purification processes become prohibitively expensive.

This study aims to optimize ON purification using ion-pair reversed-phase liquid chromatography (IP-RPLC) through both single-objective (productivity) and multi-objective (productivity and yield) optimization. The optimization focuses on two key variables: injection volume and gradient slope, under varying product purity constraints. A 20-mer ON and its six most abundant shortmer impurities were used as model compounds. A hybrid optimization strategy—combining simulated annealing (stochastic) with the simplex algorithm (deterministic)—was employed to improve search efficiency and robustness. For multi-objective optimization, the Pareto front approach was applied. Finally, the study explores how the choice of gradient calibration ranges influences optimization results and the shape of the resulting Pareto fronts.

2. Theory

The elution profiles in this study were calculated using the transport–dispersive (TD) model [5]. The differential mass transport balance for component i is expressed as follows:

$$\frac{\partial c_i}{\partial t} + F \frac{\partial q_i}{\partial t} + \frac{u}{\varepsilon_t} \frac{\partial c_i}{\partial x} = D_L \frac{\partial^2 c_i}{\partial x^2} \quad (1)$$

Here, c_i and q_i denote the concentrations of component i in the mobile and stationary phases, respectively. More specifically, c_i is expressed as mass per unit volume of mobile phase, while q_i is the amount of adsorbed component (e.g., mass in grams) per unit volume of stationary phase.

To ensure dimensional consistency in Eq. (1), the term $\partial q/\partial t$ is multiplied by the phase ratio $F = (1 - \varepsilon_t)/\varepsilon_t$, which represent the volume ratio between the stationary and mobile phases. This approach follows the standard formulation described by Guiochon et al. in *Fundamentals of Preparative and Nonlinear Chromatography* [5].

In Eq. (1), ε_t is the total column porosity, u is the superficial velocity (cm min^{-1}), and D_L is the axial dispersion coefficient ($\text{cm}^2 \text{min}^{-1}$). The Danckwerts-type boundary conditions were applied at the column inlet and outlet [18]. A linear gradient was used, as described by Åsberg et al. [19].

The organic modifier was modeled as a separate, unretained component whose transport through the column is governed solely by convection. This assumption implies that the gradient profile propagates without retention, allowing the modifier concentration to vary both temporally and spatially along the column. As a result, solute adsorption responds dynamically to the local modifier concentration at each axial position [5].

The dispersion coefficient (D_L) was estimated using the Chung and Wen correlation [20], based on the average mobile phase density and viscosity at the start and end of the gradient:

$$\frac{\varepsilon_e D_L}{uL} = \frac{\varepsilon_e d_p}{L} \frac{1}{0.2 + 0.011 \text{Re}^{0.48}} \quad (2)$$

where ε_e is the external porosity, d_p is the particle diameter, and L is the column length. The TD model requires a detailed description of the adsorption–desorption process. In this study, oligonucleotide (ON) adsorption is described using a Langmuir adsorption–desorption kinetic model. Under gradient conditions, where the organic modifier content changes over time, the adsorption model must be adjusted accordingly.

In this study, adsorption was modeled using a Langmuir-like adsorption-desorption kinetic model in which the adsorption coefficients are expressed as exponential functions of the organic modifier fraction φ in the mobile phase. The kinetic equations for the full-length product (FLP) and its main impurity (IMP) are:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial q_{\text{FLP}}}{\partial t} &= k_{a,\text{FLP}} \exp(-S_{\text{FLP}}\varphi) c_{\text{FLP}} (q_{s,0} \exp(-S_3\varphi) - q_{\text{FLP}} - q_{\text{IMP}}) - k_{d,\text{FLP}} q_{\text{FLP}} \\ &= k_{d,\text{FLP}} \left[\frac{k_{a,\text{FLP}} \exp(-S_{\text{FLP}}\varphi)}{k_{d,\text{FLP}}} c_{\text{FLP}} (q_{s,0} \exp(-S_3\varphi) - q_{\text{FLP}} - q_{\text{IMP}}) - q_{\text{FLP}} \right] \\ &= k_{d,\text{FLP}} \left[K_{\text{FLP}} \exp(-S_{\text{FLP}}\varphi) c_{\text{FLP}} (q_{s,0} \exp(-S_3\varphi) - q_{\text{FLP}} - q_{\text{IMP}}) - q_{\text{FLP}} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial q_{\text{IMP}}}{\partial t} &= k_{a,\text{IMP}} \exp(-S_{\text{IMP}}\varphi) c_{\text{IMP}} (q_{s,0} \exp(-S_3\varphi) - q_{\text{FLP}} - q_{\text{IMP}}) - k_{d,\text{IMP}} q_{\text{IMP}} \\ &= k_{d,\text{IMP}} \left[\frac{k_{a,\text{IMP}} \exp(-S_{\text{IMP}}\varphi)}{k_{d,\text{IMP}}} c_{\text{IMP}} (q_{s,0} \exp(-S_3\varphi) - q_{\text{FLP}} - q_{\text{IMP}}) - q_{\text{IMP}} \right] \\ &= k_{d,\text{IMP}} \left[K_{\text{IMP}} \exp(-S_{\text{IMP}}\varphi) c_{\text{IMP}} (q_{s,0} \exp(-S_3\varphi) - q_{\text{FLP}} - q_{\text{IMP}}) - q_{\text{IMP}} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Here k_a and k_d are the rate constants for adsorption and desorption, respectively, and $K = k_a/k_d$ is the equilibrium constant. The organic modifier fraction is denoted by φ , and the effect of φ on the equilibrium

constants for FLP and IMP is described by the empirical parameters S_{FLP} and S_{IMP} , respectively. These parameters control how each component's affinity for the stationary phase decreases as the organic modifier content increases. In addition, the maximum adsorption capacity q_s is assumed to decrease exponentially with increasing φ , according to the relationship $q_s = q_{s,0} \exp(-S_3 \varphi)$ where S_3 characterizes the modifier dependence of the total available binding capacity. While S_{FLP} and S_{IMP} are component-specific, S_3 describes a system-level property related to the stationary phase – namely, the column's overall adsorption capacity.

Under the assumption of infinitely fast adsorption–desorption kinetics, i.e., the time derivatives $\partial q_i / \partial t = 0$, Eqs. (3) and (4) reduce to a two-component Langmuir isotherm model:

$$q_{\text{FLP}} = \frac{K_{\text{FLP}} \exp(-S_{\text{FLP}} \varphi) q_{s,0} \exp(-S_3 \varphi) c_{\text{FLP}}}{1 + K_{\text{FLP}} \exp(-S_{\text{FLP}} \varphi) c_{\text{FLP}} + K_{\text{IMP}} \exp(-S_{\text{IMP}} \varphi) c_{\text{IMP}}} \quad (5)$$

$$q_{\text{IMP}} = \frac{K_{\text{IMP}} \exp(-S_{\text{IMP}} \varphi) q_{s,0} \exp(-S_3 \varphi) c_{\text{IMP}}}{1 + K_{\text{FLP}} \exp(-S_{\text{FLP}} \varphi) c_{\text{FLP}} + K_{\text{IMP}} \exp(-S_{\text{IMP}} \varphi) c_{\text{IMP}}} \quad (6)$$

These expressions describe competitive equilibrium binding under gradient conditions, with all isotherm parameters dynamically influenced by the mobile phase composition. The model has previously been applied to overloaded oligonucleotide separations and further details can be found in Leško et al. in [8].

3. Materials and methods

3.1. Chemicals and materials

A phosphodiester oligonucleotide (5'-GGTA ATCC TCAG ACGT TGCA-3'), hereafter referred to as full-length product (FLP), was synthesized using an ÄKTA Oligopilot plus 100 system (GE Healthcare, Chicago, IL, USA) along with commercially available DNA phosphoramidite building blocks and Primer Support 5 G UnyLinker (Cytiva Life Sciences, Marlborough, MA, USA). The ON was cleaved and deprotected using NH_4OH (30 % aq), filtered and washed, concentrated under vacuum, and resuspended in water to a concentration of 6.2 mM (37.9 g L^{-1}). Dibutylammonium acetate (DBuAA) was prepared from dibutylamine (≥ 99.5 %) and acetic acid (≥ 99.7 %). Uracil (> 99 %) was used as a column void volume marker. All chemicals were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). The mobile phases were prepared using HPLC-grade acetonitrile (MeCN) from VWR (Radnor, PA, USA) and deionized water with a resistivity of 18.2 $\text{M}\Omega$ cm from a Milli-Q Integral 3 water purification system (Merck Millipore, Darmstadt, Germany).

3.2. Instrumentation and column

All experiments were performed using an Agilent 1290 Infinity II equipped with two G7120A binary pumps, a temperature-regulated G7167B multisampler, a temperature-regulated G7116B column oven, a G7117B diode-array UV detector, and a G6135B single-quad electrospray ionization (ESI) mass spectrometer (MS), all from Agilent Technologies (Santa Clara, CA, USA). An XBridge C18 column (50 \times 2.1 mm, 5 μm ; Waters, Milford, MA, USA) was used.

3.3. Procedures

In the IP-RPLC experiments, mobile phase A contained 20 v % MeCN and mobile phase B contained 50 v % MeCN with 60 mM DBuAA. The column oven was set to 50 °C and the flow rate was 0.5 mL min^{-1} . UV signals were recorded at 260 and 300 nm. The effluent after the UV cell was split (approximately 1:10) and a makeup flow of 0.1 mL min^{-1} containing 70 v % MeCN with 0.1 v % ammonium hydroxide was added. MS analysis was performed in negative ESI mode, and all ions were recorded using selective ion monitoring at a charge state of -3 . The MS settings were as follows: gas temperature, 250 °C; nitrogen drying gas flow, 11 L min^{-1} ; nebulizer pressure, 25 psig; quadrupole temperature,

100 °C; and capillary voltage, 4000 V. Gradient programs started at 24.5 v % MeCN and ended at 39.5 v % followed by washing with 50 v % MeCN for at least two column volumes, then re-equilibration for at least ten column volumes. Gradient times were 10, 6, 3, 2.5, and 2 min, corresponding to slopes of 1.5, 2.5, 5, 6, and 7.5 v % MeCN min^{-1} . Sample concentrations were 0.1 and 37.9 g L^{-1} for analytical and overloaded injections, respectively. The injection volumes for overloaded experiments were 5, 6.5, and 8 μL for overloaded experiments, equivalent to 1.095, 1.423, and 1.752 mg mL^{-1} of packed stationary phase. Two replicate injections were performed. Parts of the experimental dataset were previously used in an empirical comparison with ion-exchange chromatography [21].

3.4. Calculations

The overloaded concentration profiles were simulated using the TD model, coupled with the appropriate kinetic adsorption model (see Section 2). The model equations were solved using the method of orthogonal collocation on finite elements (OCFE), which discretizes the spatial derivatives into a system of ordinary differential equations [22]. In this study, the column length was divided into 15 finite elements, with 3 collocation points per element. Increasing the number of elements or collocation points beyond these values had a negligible effect on the simulation results. The resulting system of equations was solved using the CVODE solver from the Suite of Nonlinear and Differential/Algebraic Equation Solvers (SUNDIALS) [23].

The parameters of the kinetic adsorption model were determined using the inverse method, implemented via the deterministic Levenberg–Marquardt procedure [24]. The inverse method is commonly used in chromatography to estimate parameters governing adsorption/desorption processes and mass transfer kinetics [25]. The accuracy of the estimated parameters was evaluated using 95 % confidence intervals, calculated according to the Student's t -test formulas provided by Seber [26]. The parameters were estimated using experimental data obtained at gradient slopes of 1.5, 2.5, and 7.5 % min^{-1} and injection volumes of 8, 5, and 8 μL , respectively, unless otherwise stated. The parameters of the kinetic adsorption model were determined by minimizing the sum of squared differences between experimental and calculated concentration profiles.

Before estimating the kinetic adsorption model parameters using the inverse method, UV absorbance values were converted into total concentration profiles, including both the FLP and co-eluting impurities ($n - 1$ through $n - 6$). This approach assumed that the UV absorbances of the FLP and impurities were identical, introducing a possible potential source of error. UV signals were converted to concentrations using calibration curves, determined separately at each gradient slope based on recorded elution profiles for three different injection volumes. The calibration curves were polynomial functions, including linear and quadratic terms.

To decompose the total concentration profile into individual component profiles, mass detector signals were used. The fraction x_i of component i at each point in time in the elution profile was calculated using:

$$x_i = \frac{m_i}{\sum m_i}, \quad i = \text{FLP}, n - 1, n - 2, \dots, n - 6 \quad (7)$$

where m_i is the mass signal recorded for component i . It was assumed that the concentration dependence of the mass signal was the same for all components. The individual concentration profile of each ON was then determined by multiplying the total concentration profile by the fraction x_i :

$$c_i = x_i c, \quad i = \text{FLP}, n - 1, n - 2, \dots, n - 6 \quad (8)$$

where c is the total concentration of ONs determined from the UV signal and calibration curve.

The validated mathematical model was subsequently used in optimizing the chromatographic process. As an objective function in the optimization, the productivity (Pr), defined as the grams of FLP collected per minute normalized to the column cross-section, was used. Moreover, in the multi-objective optimization, the yield (Y) of the process, defined as the ratio of the mass of FLP collected at the column end to its mass introduced at the column inlet, was taken into account. In the optimization process, the time needed for washing and equilibrating the column was not considered. The results therefore express the highest theoretical values of the process. In this study, the productivity of the chromatographic process was considered to depend on two factors. The optimized parameters were the injection time (t_{inj} [min]), which determines the injection volume (V_{inj} [μL]), and the gradient time (t_g [min]), which determines the gradient slope (β [% MeCN min^{-1}]). This formulation keeps the initial and final modifier concentrations fixed while varying the gradient time to define the slope. This is a standard and robust approach in gradient optimization, as it avoids scenarios where solutes fail to elute or are insufficiently resolved. Allowing the final modifier concentration to vary freely would require additional experimental calibration and could generate unrealistic or non-eluting conditions.

The optimization problem comes down to the following expression:

$$\text{Max}(Pr) = f(t_{inj}, t_g) \quad (9)$$

The optimized parameters were constrained by the following boundary: $t_{inj} \in [0.04, 0.016]$, $t_g \in [2, 16]$. Thus, the restrictions correspond to an injection volume between 2 and 8 μL and a gradient slope between 0.94 and 7.5 % min^{-1} . Note that the boundary conditions in the numerical optimization were extended beyond the experimental conditions. The injection volume in the experiments was between 5 and 8 μL while the gradient time was between 2 and 10 min. Moreover, the following product purities were introduced as constraints in the optimization process: 95, 96, 97, 98, and 99 %. In all optimizations, the hybrid method of the simulated annealing algorithm with the simplex method was used [12].

Finally, it could be worthwhile to mention that the optimization algorithm handled the decision space robustly, even though the two decision variables— injection time and gradient time— differed in scale by 2–3 orders of magnitude. No numerical instabilities were observed during the approximately 20,000 simulations performed in the optimization process.

4. Results and discussion

This section is organized into five parts. Section 4.1 characterizes the ON and its impurities. Section 4.2 presents the predicted overloaded concentration profiles of ONs. Section 4.3 discusses the results of the optimization process, while Section 4.4 focuses on multi-objective optimization. Finally, Section 4.5 addresses the observed phenomena resulting from the multi-objective optimization.

4.1. Characterization of the oligonucleotides and chromatographic system

The crude ON was analyzed using LC-MS under previously described conditions [8]. The analysis revealed numerous impurities (Fig. S1, Table S1, Supplementary material), indicating a purity of 81.9 % for the FLP. The remaining sample comprised various shortmers. The six most abundant impurities eluting closest to the FLP ($n-1$ through $n-6$) were selected for further study (Table S1).

4.2. Numerical model validation

To achieve the aim of this study, a model was first developed that could predict chromatograms with sufficient accuracy for process optimization. Accurately modeling the elution bands of the FLP and six

impurities, as shown in Fig. 1, is nearly impossible—or at the very least, highly impractical. Explicitly modeling all seven components would require estimation of 23 parameters in the kinetic adsorption model (see Section 2), which is a large number for inverse modeling. Reliable estimation would further require accurate initial guesses for each parameter to ensure convergence.

In addition, including all seven components would dramatically increase the number of partial differential equations in the mass balance system, thereby significantly extending computation times during both parameter estimation and optimization. This trade-off cannot be ignored in practical applications. A suitable model must strike a balance between descriptive accuracy and computational efficiency.

In our case, perfectly resolving all individual elution profiles was not necessary. Instead, a model was needed that could reproduce key concentration trends while remaining tractable for optimization. Therefore, the six closely eluting impurities were lumped into a single pseudo-component, resulting in a two-component system (FLP + IMP), as illustrated by the red dashed line in Fig. 1. This simplification significantly reduced model complexity and enabled efficient numerical optimization without sacrificing predictive utility.

To predict elution bands, mass balance equations coupled with the kinetic description of the adsorption–desorption process were applied. The experimental conditions and the values of the basic model parameters used in the simulations are presented in Table S2 for the mobile and stationary phases. Due to the broadened elution bands observed in this study, the commonly used equilibrium–dispersive (ED) model—often applied in preparative chromatography [5]—was not suitable. Instead, we consistently employed the transport–dispersive (TD) model coupled with a kinetic adsorption–desorption description, as introduced in Section 2. The broadened profiles suggested a slow adsorption–desorption process, leading to the application of a kinetic adsorption–desorption model, which provided to good results (see Eqs. (3) and 4).

For simplicity, a constant monolayer saturation capacity is often assumed when modeling overloaded elution bands. However, in this case, the saturation capacity was influenced by the modifier concentration in the eluent (see Section 2). Introducing a saturation capacity dependent on the modifier concentration significantly improved the

Fig. 1. The elution profiles of FLP and six main impurities recorded using mass detection. The sum of the impurities is shown by the red dashed line. The gradient slope is 5 % min^{-1} and the injection volume is 8 μL .

agreement between the calculated and experimental elution profiles [8].

Fig. 2 shows overlapping chromatograms from experimental (dotted lines) and calculated (solid lines) elution profiles at different injection volumes and gradient slopes: 1.5, 2.5, and 7.5 % min⁻¹. Comparisons additional gradient slopes (i.e., 5 and 6 % min⁻¹) are provided in Fig. S2. The parameters of the kinetic adsorption–desorption model, determined using the inverse method, are presented in Table 1. With these parameters, the model is able to accurately predict the overloaded concentration profiles of the FLP (black lines) and the lumped impurity (red lines) across all tested gradient slopes and injection volumes.

To quantitatively assess model performance, we calculated the average area of overlap between experimental and simulated concentration profiles. These values were 95 % for the FLP and 87 % for the impurity, indicating good predictive agreement. Slightly lower agreement was observed only at the steepest gradient slope (7.5 % min⁻¹), suggesting that a more advanced model may be required to accurately

Table 1

Estimated parameters of the isotherm model (see Eqs. (3) and (4)).

Parameters	Value	95 % confidence interval of Student's <i>t</i> -test
$k_{d,1}$ [min ⁻¹]	$9.138746 \cdot 10^0$	$4.778 \cdot 10^{-1}$
K_1 [L g ⁻¹]	$2.856954 \cdot 10^4$	$1.396 \cdot 10^3$
$k_{d,2}$ [min ⁻¹]	$1.091465 \cdot 10^1$	$2.113 \cdot 10^{-1}$
K_2 [L g ⁻¹]	$1.548738 \cdot 10^5$	$3.221 \cdot 10^3$
S_1	$3.672297 \cdot 10^1$	$2.436 \cdot 10^{-1}$
S_2	$4.081585 \cdot 10^1$	$8.619 \cdot 10^{-2}$
$q_{s,0}$ [g L ⁻¹]	$2.430622 \cdot 10^2$	$9.890 \cdot 10^0$
S_3	$1.236775 \cdot 10^1$	$1.532 \cdot 10^{-1}$

Fig. 2. Comparison between experimental (dotted lines) and calculated (solid lines) elution profiles of FLP (black lines) and lumped impurities (red lines) at a sample concentration of 37.926 g L⁻¹ and injection volumes of 5 μL (a, b, c; first row), 6.5 μL (d, e, f; second row), and 8 μL (g, h, i; third row). The gradient slopes are 7.5 % min⁻¹ (a, d, g; first column), 2.5 % min⁻¹ (b, e, h; second column), and 1.5 % min⁻¹ (c, f, and i; third column). The elution profiles were calculated using the kinetic adsorption–desorption model (see Eqs. (3) and (4)). The parameters of the model are presented in Table 1.

capture faster elution dynamics—this point is further discussed in Section 4.5.

4.3. Optimization of the chromatographic process

The validated model from Section 4.2 was used to numerically determine the maximum productivity as a function of gradient time and injection time (see Eq. (9)). Given the likely presence of multiple local optima in this response space, a hybrid optimization strategy—previously described in Section 1—was used to ensure reliable convergence. This approach combines simulated annealing with the simplex algorithm to balance global search with local refinement. The results of the optimization are presented in Table 2 under purity constraints ranging from 95 to 99 %.

As shown in Table 2, productivity increases with lower purity constraints. Reducing the purity from 99 to 95 % results in a more than fourfold increase in productivity. Regardless of the purity constraints, the optimum is consistently achieved using the largest possible injection volume (the right boundary) in the optimization. The numerical model suggests that even larger injection volumes could be beneficial. However, experimental results indicate that increasing the injection volume beyond this point leads to unresolved sample breakthrough.

The gradient time, on the other hand, increases with higher purity constraints, see Table 2. Under the two lowest purity constraints (95 and 96 %), the optimal gradient time corresponds to the shortest duration under consideration (the left boundary). Under higher purity constraints, the optimal gradient time increases significantly with increasing purity requirements. This behavior is attributed to the improvement in selectivity with decreasing gradient slope. As illustrated in Figs. 2 and S2 (Supplementary material), the high-concentration region of the FLP co-elutes with impurity. Consequently, when high-purity products are required, the selectivity factor plays a critical role in achieving the desired product.

Table 2 also shows a decrease in yield as the purity constraint becomes more stringent, ranging from 50.7 % to 25.5 %. This trend can be attributed to the limited selectivity between the FLP and its impurities under the experimental conditions. Experimental validation of the optimized conditions was not performed, as these conditions lie at or near the boundaries of the gradient and injection time ranges already used to generate the experimental data on which the model was calibrated and validated.

4.4. Multi-objective optimization

As shown in Table 2, optimizing only for productivity yields poor results in terms of process yield. To address this, we applied a multi-objective optimization strategy—described in Section 1—that considers both productivity and yield simultaneously. This approach enabled us to evaluate trade-offs between the two outcomes. The results are visualized as Pareto plots, illustrating productivity as a function of yield.

Fig. 3a and 3b show the Pareto plots for product purities set to 96 and 98 %, respectively. Additional results for purities of 95, 97, and 99 % are

Table 2

Optimum gradient time (t_g) and injection time (t_{inj}) for FLP purification according to the criterion of maximal productivity for different product purity settings. The data are complemented by the yield calculated for optimal conditions.

Set Purity [%]	Productivity $\bullet 10^{-3}$ [g min $^{-1}$ cm $^{-2}$]	Yield [%]	t_g [min]	t_{inj} [min]
95	4.091	50.73	2	0.0160
96	3.286	37.43	2	0.0160
97	2.158	25.54	2.274	0.01599
98	1.498	36.27	6.415	0.0160
99	0.8925	28.13	10.67	0.0160

presented in Fig. S3 (Supplementary material). Each point in the figures represents a simulation with a unique set of parameters (gradient time and injection time), with approximately 20,000 simulations in total used to calculate productivity and yield. In our case, one simulation took approximately 4 s to complete.

The Pareto-optimal solutions are located on the frontier of the Pareto plots, representing the conditions under which maximum productivity is achieved for a given yield. These optimal conditions are highlighted in Fig. 4a and 4b under purity constraints of 96 and 98 %, respectively. Results for other product purities are shown in Fig. S4 (Supplementary material).

The Pareto front enables us to find the optimum conditions under which two factors are optimized. The trade-off between productivity and yield is clearly shown. Under a 96 % purity constraint (Fig. 4a), the maximum productivity is achieved at a low yield of about 37 %. Decreasing the productivity leads to increased yield. To find the best conditions, one must decide which factor is more important; for example, if the product is very expensive to produce, sacrificing productivity for yield can be a good option.

The experimental conditions identified on the Pareto front are summarized in Fig. 4. These include the injection time (c, d), gradient time (e, f), collected mass during one cycle (g, h), and cycle time (i, j) as functions of yield for Pareto front purity constraints of 96 % (left column figures) and 98 % (right column figures), respectively. Corresponding plots for other purity constraints are presented in Fig. S4.

As shown in Fig. 4c and d, the injection time increases sharply with increasing yield and quickly reaches its maximum value (restricted by the right boundary) during the optimization for nearly all considered product purities. Over much of the investigated yield range, the optimal injection time remains at this maximum value. Instead in this region, the yield is increased by increasing the gradient time, which starts from the steepest gradient (minimum value of 2 min) and gradually increases with yield until reaching the shallowest gradient (maximum value of 16 min). As illustrated in Fig. 4g and h, in the yield region at constant injection time, the collected mass of the target product during one cycle increases with longer gradient times due to the improved selectivity. However, longer gradient times result in increased cycle times (Fig. 4i and j).

When the gradient time reaches its maximum value, the injection time begins to decrease. Achieving higher yield therefore requires that the gradient time remain at its maximum while the injection time is reduced. A smaller injection volume improves the column's separation performance, allowing for a higher process yield. However, increasing the yield comes at the cost of reduced productivity, driven by a decrease in the collected mass per cycle.

4.5. Pareto front: different shapes

By examining Fig. 4 (and the corresponding Fig. S4 in the Supplementary material), an additional noteworthy observation emerges. The plots of productivity versus yield exhibit an inflection point or local minimum within the range of the constant injection time. These inflection points occur at yields of 0.53, 0.44, 0.35, 0.24, and 0.12 for product purities of 95, 96, 97, 98 %, and 99 %, respectively.

The shape of the Pareto fronts suggests that they consist of two distinct regions. Here we hypothesize that, due to the slow kinetic of the separation system, our model (Eqs. (3) and 4) cannot properly describe the separation process at all gradient slopes considered here. When inspecting the model fit (see Fig. 2 and Section 4.2), we already observed that the model's ability to predict elution profiles at steeper gradients was not as good as at shallower gradients.

To test this hypothesis, two new models were calibrated, the first using only experimental data obtained at shallow gradients (6 and 10 min) and the second using steep gradients (2 and 3 min). The validation of the models from these estimations is presented in Fig. S4. Using these models under a 98 % purity constraint, Pareto plots were generated from

Fig. 3. Pareto curves (red lines), i.e., Productivity (Pr [$\text{g min}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$]) versus Yield, for product purities of: a) 96 % and b) 98 %. The scattered points show the results of the multi-objective optimization of Pr and Yield using the simulated annealing method with the simplex algorithm. Subplots (c, d), (e, f), (g, h), and (i, j) present injection time [min], gradient time [min], collected mass [g cm^{-2}] during one cycle, and cycle time [min], respectively, for the Pareto curves. The first and second columns present the results for product purities of 96 and 98 %, respectively.

Fig. 4. Pareto curves (red lines), i.e., Productivity (Pr [g min $^{-1}$ cm $^{-2}$]) versus Yield, at a product purity of 98 %, and: a) the model parameters determined based on data obtained at gradient slopes of 5 and 7.5 % min $^{-1}$; b) the model parameters determined based on data obtained at gradient slopes of 1.5 and 2.5 % min $^{-1}$. The scattered points show the results of the multi-objective optimization of Pr and Yield using the simulated annealing method with the simplex algorithm. Subplots (c, d), (e, f), (g, h), and (i, j) present injection time [min], gradient time [min], and collected mass [g cm $^{-2}$] during one cycle, and cycle time [min], respectively, for the Pareto curves. The first and second columns present the results for the Pareto curves presented in a) and b), respectively.

a model using steep (Fig. 4a) and shallow (Fig. 4b) gradients. The optimizations carried out for a purity of 97 % are presented in Fig. S5.

As shown in Fig. 4a, and b, the curvature of the plots is smooth, with no local minimum or inflection point, in contrast to previous observation (cf. Fig. 3a and b). Additionally, the Pareto plots obtained for steep (Fig. 4a) and shallow (Fig. 4b) gradients predict significantly different maximum productivity versus yield.

One possible explanation for this phenomenon is the establishment of different equilibrium states at varying gradient slopes. When the concentration of the organic modifier remains constant, the equilibrium state is fully established. However, during gradient changes, new equilibrium states are generated, but are not fully established. The steeper the gradient is, the further the system is from equilibrium. If model parameters are estimated based on a narrow range of gradient times and then extrapolated, the resulting Pareto curves are smooth, lacking inflection points, as observed in Fig. 4. However, when model parameters are estimated across the entire gradient range (from 1.5 to 7.5 % min⁻¹), the model tries to account for the different equilibrium states encountered during elution, revealing varied Pareto curve shapes at both steep and shallow gradient slopes. In this case, the process is primarily controlled by gradient time, which affects the shape and retention of the overloaded elution profile from which the Pareto curve is calculated. Additionally, the visibility of the extreme point increases as the product purity decreases. This is because the calculation of collected mass of FLP and cycle time is more influenced when the product purity is set to 95 % rather than 99 %. Although the model exhibits certain limitations, it remains a useful tool for optimizing oligonucleotide separations using ion-pair chromatography—provided that separate parameter sets are used for different gradient regimes especially for those that differ significantly. This outcome highlights the need for continued research to deepen the mechanistic understanding of oligonucleotide retention in IPC, particularly under gradient conditions, and to support the development of more advanced adsorption models capable of accurately describing a broader range of gradient slopes.

5. Conclusion

This study utilized numerical tools to optimize IP-RPLC for separating a 20-mer ON from the six most abundant impurities from synthesis (81.9 % LC-MS purity). To simplify the numerical calculations, the elution profiles of these six impurities were lumped into a single component. The transport–dispersive model was applied to calculate elution profiles with high accuracy.

First, single-objective optimization was performed to identify the maximum productivity under purity constraints of 95–99 %. A hybrid method combining simulated annealing with the simplex algorithm was used. Results indicated that maximal productivity occurred at the highest injection volume across all purity levels, and that the optimal gradient time increased with increasing purity constraints. As purity constraints increased, the selectivity factor became more critical, leading to a flatter gradient slope. Notably, decreasing purity constraints from 99 to 95 % resulted in a fourfold increase in productivity. However, in all cases, the yield of the optimum process was relatively low, decreasing from 51 to 28 % with stricter purity constraints.

The trade-off between productivity and yield was analyzed using multi-objective optimization, presented as a Pareto plot. A sharp decline in productivity was observed with increasing yield. A recent comparative study of preparative IP-RPLC and ion-exchange chromatography (IEX) highlighted that IEX can offer significantly higher productivity, albeit with lower resolution [21]. This finding supports the idea of combining IEX and IP-RPLC in an integrated workflow, where IEX acts as a high-capacity capture step and IP-RPLC as a high-resolution polishing step. Their relative orthogonality may enhance selectivity and final product purity, while IEX also contributes to sample concentration upstream of polishing. To further enhance productivity and yield, alternative strategies should be explored—including different IP-RPLC

systems, standalone IEX, integrated IEX–IP-RPLC workflows, and continuous processing approaches.

The Pareto plots exhibited an inflection point or local minimum under conditions where the injection time was at its maximum. We hypothesized that, due to the slow kinetics of the separation system, our model could not accurately describe the process across the full range of gradient slopes considered. To test this hypothesis, two new models were calibrated—one using only experimental data from shallow gradients and the other from steep gradients. The resulting Pareto fronts displayed no inflection points or local minima, suggesting that our hypothesis cannot be ruled out.

This study highlights the need for a deeper fundamental understanding of ON separation using IP-RPLC. It underscores the importance of continuous improvement in chromatographic modeling and thorough investigation of the underlying separation mechanisms. It also demonstrates the importance of an accurate column model for enabling reliable numerical process optimization.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Marek Leško: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Martin Enmark:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Krzysztof Kaczmarek:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Software, Project administration, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Jörgen Samuelsson:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Torgny Fornstedt:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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